

DETECTION-ESTIMATION OF MORE UNCORRELATED GAUSSIAN SOURCES THAN SENSORS USING PARTIALLY AUGMENTABLE SPARSE ANTENNA ARRAYS

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ABSTRACT

We introduce a new approach for the detection-estimation problem for “partially augmentable” nonuniform linear antenna arrays, whose set of intersensor differences is not complete. We propose a positive-definite completion method of the partially specified M_α -variate Toeplitz covariance matrix via direct augmentation, followed by its transformation into a sequence of positive-definite Toeplitz matrices T_μ , each having their $(M_\alpha - \mu)$ smallest eigenvalues equalised, and so being an appropriate candidate for the number of sources μ . Likelihood ratio information criteria (AIC, MDL and MAP) are then used to select the best candidate model, simultaneously providing DOA estimates for the indicated number of sources.

1 INTRODUCTION

In our previous papers [1, 2], we introduced a new approach for detection-estimation of a *superior* number of uncorrelated Gaussian sources ($m \geq M$, where M is the number of sensors) for the class of *fully augmentable* nonuniform linear arrays (NLA’s). Such geometries belong to the family “minimum redundancy” arrays [3], and are defined as having no gaps in the set of $M(M - 1)/2$ intersensor separations, in other words as having a full (complete) co-array that is identical to the corresponding M_α -sensor uniform linear array (ULA), with $M_\alpha \gg M$.

In this paper, we extend our approach to the contrary class of *partially augmentable* NLA’s that are typically not redundant, but rather have some number of missing lags [4]. The five-sensor so-called “minimum-gaps” NLA [4]

$$\mathbf{d}_5 = [0, 1, 4, 9, 11] \quad (1)$$

measured in half-wavelength units is used in this paper as an example geometry.

Naturally, application of the direct augmentation approach (DAA) of Pillai *et al.* [5], intended for use with fully augmentable arrays, results in some number of missing diagonals in the covariance matrix. In our example, we have a single missing covariance lag corre-

sponding to the difference six:

$$T_0 = \text{Toep}[r_0, r_1, \dots, r_5, r_7, \dots, r_{11}]. \quad (2)$$

Let $N_{\max}$ be defined such that all lags up to and including $N_{\max}$ are presented by the array geometry ($N_{\max} = 5$ in our example). Clearly, when $m > N_{\max}$, no existing technique for detection-estimation is directly applicable. The philosophy behind our approach presented here is quite straight-forward, and essentially combines two techniques proposed earlier [4, 1].

Given the incomplete set of M_α observable spatial covariance lags $\hat{\mathbf{t}}$, we firstly find the “minimum-defective” positive-definite (p.d.) completion. Typically, feasibility conditions for p.d. completion are not met by a set of sample covariance lags in $\hat{T}_0$, and the specified (observed) lags need to be modified. Minimum-defective completion minimises the Euclidean norm of the introduced perturbations, and is not directly related to the likelihood ratio (LR). For this reason, our next step is to find another M_α -variate p.d. Toeplitz matrix $\hat{T}_{ML}$ with maximum LR. Of course, we can claim only a local optimality for the proposed solution.

Note that $\hat{T}_{ML}$ almost certainly does not have the appropriate structure to represent m uncorrelated plane waves plus white noise, *ie.* does not have noise subspace eigenvalues that are equal, hence our third step is to construct a set of proper candidate models, *ie.* p.d. Toeplitz matrices $\{\hat{T}_\mu\}$ ($\mu = 1, \dots, M_\alpha - 1$), each having their $(M_\alpha - \mu)$ smallest eigenvalues equalised. Naturally, this transformation involves not only the missing lags, but the specified lags as well, and leads to a degradation in LR compared with $\hat{T}_{ML}$. The final step is to use traditional information (AIC, MDL) or Bayesian (MAP) [6] criteria to select the “optimum” candidate model, which uniquely defines the DOA’s for its μ sources.

In this paper, we assume that identifiability conditions are met, that is, an incomplete Toeplitz matrix (with the exact specified lags) has a unique completion. In general, this is not necessarily true, however identifiability for detection purposes leads beyond the limits of this paper, and is discussed elsewhere [2, 7].

2 PROBLEM FORMULATION

Consider an M -element NLA with sensors located at positions

$$\mathbf{d} \equiv [d_1 \equiv 0, d_2, \dots, d_M \equiv M_\alpha - 1] \quad (3)$$

restricted to integer values measured in half-wavelength units ($\lambda/2$). We assume that Gaussian processes are observed as a combination of m uncorrelated plane waves with DOA's $\boldsymbol{\theta} \equiv [\theta_1, \dots, \theta_m]^T$, powers $P \equiv \text{diag}[p_1, \dots, p_m]$ and Gaussian white noise of power p_0 :

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = S(\boldsymbol{\theta})\mathbf{x}(t) + \boldsymbol{\eta}(t) \quad \text{for } t = 1, \dots, N \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{y}(t) \in \mathcal{C}^{M \times 1}$ is the vector of observed sensor outputs (the ‘‘snapshot’’), $\mathbf{x}(t) \in \mathcal{C}^{M_\alpha \times 1}$ is the vector of Gaussian signal amplitudes

$$\mathcal{E}\{\mathbf{x}(t_1)\mathbf{x}^H(t_2)\} = \begin{cases} P & \text{for } t_1 = t_2 \\ 0 & \text{for } t_1 \neq t_2, \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

$\boldsymbol{\eta}(t) \in \mathcal{C}^{M \times 1}$ is additive white Gaussian noise, $\mathcal{C}^{p \times q}$ is the space of $p \times q$ complex-valued matrices, and $\mathcal{E}\{\cdot\}$ is the expectation operator. The array manifold matrix is $S(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \equiv [\mathbf{s}(\theta_1), \dots, \mathbf{s}(\theta_m)] \in \mathcal{C}^{M \times m}$, where each

$$\mathbf{s}(\theta_j) = \left[1, \exp(i\pi d_2 \sin \theta_j), \dots, \exp(i\pi d_M \sin \theta_j) \right]^T \quad (6)$$

is a so-called steering vector. The set of independent snapshots $\mathbf{y}(t) \in \mathcal{C}^{M \times 1}$ originate from a complex Gaussian distribution $\mathcal{CN}(M, 0, R)$, where

$$R = S(\boldsymbol{\theta})PS(\boldsymbol{\theta})^H + p_0I_M. \quad (7)$$

Given N independent snapshots, the sufficient statistic for DOA estimation is the DDC (sample) matrix

$$\hat{R} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N \mathbf{y}(t)\mathbf{y}^H(t). \quad (8)$$

For the corresponding M_α -element ULA, the array manifold matrix $A(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \equiv [\mathbf{a}(\theta_1), \dots, \mathbf{a}(\theta_m)] \in \mathcal{C}^{M_\alpha \times m}$ is of Vandermonde structure, with

$$\mathbf{a}(\theta_j) = \left[1, \exp(i\pi w_j), \dots, \exp(i\pi[M_\alpha - 1]w_j) \right]^T \quad (9)$$

where the spatial frequency is $w_j \equiv \sin \theta_j$. By definition, the M -element NLA can be viewed as a subarray of the M_α -element ULA. Thus the M -variate snapshot vector $\mathbf{y}(t)$ can be presented as a subset of the M_α -variate ULA output $\mathbf{Y}(t) \in \mathcal{C}^{M_\alpha \times 1}$:

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = L\mathbf{Y}(t) \quad (10)$$

where L is the $M \times M_\alpha$ binary selection (or incidence) matrix with L_{jk} equal to unity in the j^{th} row and d_k^{th} column, and zero otherwise. Correspondingly, the M -variate covariance matrix R is linked to the M_α -variate

Toeplitz covariance matrix T for the M_α -element ULA by the linear transformation

$$R = LTL^T \quad (11)$$

with

$$T = A(\boldsymbol{\theta})PA(\boldsymbol{\theta})^H + p_0I_{M_\alpha}. \quad (12)$$

The philosophy of the DAA [5] is to estimate the Toeplitz matrix covariance lags

$$\hat{T} = \{\hat{t}_{j-k}\}_{j,k=1}^{M_\alpha} \quad (13)$$

by simply averaging over the set of corresponding (possibly redundant) covariance lags taken from $\hat{R}$:

$$\hat{t}_{j-k=\kappa} = \frac{\sum_{j,k} \hat{R}_{jk} \delta(\kappa, d_j - d_k)}{\sum_{j,k} \delta(\kappa, d_j - d_k)}, \quad j > k, \quad \kappa \in \mathcal{S} \quad (14)$$

where $\delta(a, b)$ is the generalized Kronecker delta function, $\mathcal{S} = \{\kappa : \hat{t}_\kappa \text{ is specified}\}$, and $\bar{\mathcal{S}} = \{\kappa : \hat{t}_\kappa \text{ is unspecified}\}$.

Suppose for the moment that given the incomplete set of covariance lags $\hat{t}_\kappa$ ($\kappa \in \mathcal{S}$), we somehow generate the set of candidate M_α -variate p.d. Toeplitz matrices T_μ ($\mu = 1, \dots, M_\alpha - 2$) with equal $(M_\alpha - \mu)$ minimum eigenvalues. To select the best model, we compute the LR for the corresponding M -variate Hermitian matrices R_μ via (11).

We use the sphericity test:

$$H_0 : \mathcal{E}\left\{R_\mu^{-\frac{1}{2}} \hat{R} R_\mu^{-\frac{1}{2}}\right\} = p_0I_M \quad \text{against}$$

$$H_1 : \mathcal{E}\left\{R_\mu^{-\frac{1}{2}} \hat{R} R_\mu^{-\frac{1}{2}}\right\} \neq p_0I_M, \quad p_0 > 0 \quad (15)$$

with the LR

$$\gamma(T_\mu) = \frac{\det(R_\mu^{-1} \hat{R})}{\left[\frac{1}{M} \text{Tr}(R_\mu^{-1} \hat{R})\right]^M}. \quad (16)$$

Now information or Bayesian criteria may be used for model selection, such as the minimum description length [6]

$$\hat{m}_{MDL} = \arg \min_{\mu=0, \dots, M_\alpha-2} \left[-\log \gamma(T_\mu) + \frac{3}{2} \mu \log N \right]. \quad (17)$$

Obviously this approach is optimal only if T_μ is the maximum likelihood (ML) estimate of the p.d. Toeplitz matrix with equal $(M_\alpha - \mu)$ minimum eigenvalues. Since exact ML estimates of this kind are not yet known, our problem is to generate a set of above-described Toeplitz matrices T_μ sufficiently close to the sufficient statistics $\hat{R}$ in the ML sense.

3 PROPOSED ALGORITHM

The proposed algorithm for ‘‘Pisarenko’’ completion of a partially specified Toeplitz matrix with sample lags consists of three major steps.

Step 1: Given the incomplete sample covariance matrix $\hat{T}_0$, we find the minimum-deflective p.d. Toeplitz completion $\hat{T}_{pd}$ using a modified ‘‘cutting-plane’’ (convex programming) algorithm; see [4] for its explicit description and discussions.

Step 2: Next we modify $\hat{T}_{pd}$ so as to maximise the LR (16), obtaining $\hat{T}_{ML}$. Again we mention that only a local extremum can be guaranteed for this unstructured ML estimate with almost certainly all different noise eigenvalues.

Step 3: Next we modify $\hat{T}_{ML}$ in order to find the sequence of minimally perturbed matrices $\{\hat{T}_\mu\}$ ($\mu = 1, \dots, M_\alpha - 2$), each having their $(M_\alpha - \mu)$ smallest eigenvalues equalised. This linear programming (LP) routine has also been previously discussed (for the fully augmentable case) in [1, 2]; thus only Step 2 needs to be described here.

4 ML COMPLETION METHOD

According to (16), ML maximisation could be interpreted as attempting to equalise all M eigenvalues of the sample matrix

$$\hat{G} = \hat{R}^{-\frac{1}{2}}(LTL^H)\hat{R}^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad (18)$$

in the neighbourhood of the initial point $\hat{T}_{pd}$. Since any admissible perturbations are obviously different for the specified and the unspecified lags in $\hat{T}_{pd}$, we treat these two types of lags separately in the following two-stage procedure.

4.1 Step 2(a)

Here we optimise only the unspecified lags in $\hat{T}_{pd}$ until some local extremum is achieved for the function

$$\Delta(T) = \lambda_{\max}(\hat{G}) - \lambda_{\min}(\hat{G}). \quad (19)$$

Let T_k be the p.d. Toeplitz matrix obtained as the solution to this minimisation problem at the k^{th} iteration, and we use the minimum-deflective p.d. completion (‘‘Step 1’’ in [4]) with initial point $T_0 = \hat{T}_{pd}$.

The set of all possible completions may be written as

$$T_{k+1}(z) = T_k + \sum_{\kappa \in \bar{S}} (z_\kappa E_+^\kappa + \bar{z}_\kappa E_-^\kappa) > 0 \quad (20)$$

where

$$E_+ = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & & & \\ & 0 & \ddots & & \\ & & \ddots & \ddots & \\ & & & 1 & \\ & & & & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad E_- = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & & & & \\ 1 & 0 & & & \\ & \ddots & \ddots & & \\ & & \ddots & \ddots & \\ & & & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (21)$$

or in terms of real variables

$$T_{k+1}(z) = T_k + \sum_{\kappa \in \bar{S}} (\mathcal{R}e z_\kappa F_\kappa^+ + \mathcal{I}m z_\kappa F_\kappa^-) \quad (22)$$

where

$$F_\kappa^+ = E_+^\kappa + E_-^\kappa, \quad F_\kappa^- = E_+^\kappa - E_-^\kappa. \quad (23)$$

It is well known that the set of Toeplitz Hermitian matrices is congruent to the set of real symmetric matrices via the unitary transform

$$Q = \mathcal{R}e T + J_p \mathcal{I}m T = HTH^H, \quad T = H^H Q H \quad (24)$$

where

$$H = \frac{1}{2}[(I + J_p) + i(I - J_p)], \quad H^H H = I \quad (25)$$

and

$$J_p = \begin{bmatrix} & & & & 1 \\ & & & & \\ & & & & \\ & & & & \\ 1 & & & & \end{bmatrix} \quad (26)$$

is a permutation matrix. Evidently,

$$\det Q = \det(HTH^H) = \det T, \quad \text{eig}(T) = \text{eig}(Q). \quad (27)$$

Instead of modifying the complex Toeplitz matrix T , we may therefore modify the real symmetric matrix Q :

$$Q_{k+1}(x) = HT_{k+1}(z)H^H \quad (28)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= HT_k H^H + \sum_{\kappa \in \bar{S}} (x'_\kappa F_+^\kappa + x''_\kappa J_p F_-^\kappa) > 0 \quad (29) \\ &\equiv HT_k H^H + \sum_{\kappa=1}^{2p} x_\kappa F_\kappa \quad (30) \end{aligned}$$

where

$$x'_\kappa = \mathcal{R}e z_\kappa, \quad x''_\kappa = \mathcal{I}m z_\kappa, \quad F_+^\kappa = (F_\kappa^+)^T, \quad F_-^\kappa = (F_\kappa^-)^T \quad (31)$$

$$x_\kappa \equiv [x'_\kappa, x''_\kappa], \quad F_\kappa \equiv [F_+^\kappa, F_-^\kappa]. \quad (32)$$

For sufficiently small x_κ ($|x_\kappa| < \varepsilon$; $\kappa = 1, \dots, 2p$), we may treat the term

$$\sum_{\kappa=1}^{2p} x_\kappa F_\kappa = \delta(x_\kappa) \quad (33)$$

as a perturbation of the matrix Q_k . With respect to (24) and (33), we can now write the next ML-maximisation iteration of the p.d. Hermitian matrix as

$$G_{k+1} = G_k + \hat{R}^{-\frac{1}{2}} L H^H \sum_{\kappa=1}^{2p} x_\kappa F_\kappa H L^H \hat{R}^{-\frac{1}{2}}. \quad (34)$$

For sufficiently small x_κ , we use the first-order perturbation expansion for the eigenvalues:

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_j(G_{k+1}) &= \lambda_j(G_k) + \\ &\sum_{\kappa=1}^{2p} x_\kappa L_j^H(k) \hat{R}^{-\frac{1}{2}} L H^H F_\kappa H L^H \hat{R}^{-\frac{1}{2}} L_j(k) \quad (35) \end{aligned}$$

where $L_j(k)$ is the j^{th} eigenvector of G_k . Finally, introducing the $(M \times 2p)$ matrix

$$\mathcal{D}_k = \left\{ L_j^H(k) \hat{R}^{-\frac{1}{2}} L H^H F_\kappa H L^H \hat{R}^{-\frac{1}{2}} L_j(k) \right\}_{\kappa=1, \dots, 2p}^{j=1, \dots, M} \quad (36)$$

and the $2p$ -variate real vector x to formulate the following LP problem

$$\begin{aligned} \text{find } \min(\alpha - \beta) \quad & \text{subject to } \alpha > 0, \beta > 0 \quad \text{and} \\ & \Lambda_k + \mathcal{D}_k x < \alpha \mathbf{1}, \quad \Lambda_k + \mathcal{D}_k x > \beta \mathbf{1} \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

where $\mathbf{1} = [1, \dots, 1]^T$ and $|x_\kappa| < \varepsilon$; $\kappa = 1, \dots, 2p$. This iteration produces the best possible unspecified lags in $\hat{T}_{pd}$ (in some neighbourhood), obtaining the matrix T^* .

4.2 Step 2(b)

We now modify *all* $2(M_\alpha - 1)$ real entries of the matrix T^* using the same routine (37) except that the dimensions of the real vector x and matrix $\mathcal{D}_k$ are now equal to $2(M_\alpha - 1)$ and $M \times 2(M_\alpha - 1)$ respectively:

$$\mathcal{D}_k = \left\{ L_j^H(k) \hat{R}^{-\frac{1}{2}} L H^H F_\kappa H L^H \hat{R}^{-\frac{1}{2}} L_j(k) \right\}_{\kappa=1, \dots, 2(M_\alpha - 1)}^{j=1, \dots, M} \quad (39)$$

5 SIMULATION RESULTS

We consider the challenging superior scenario of $\mathbf{d}_5$ with

$$\mathbf{w} \equiv \sin \boldsymbol{\theta} = [-0.90, -0.68, -0.46, -0.24, -0.02, w_6] \quad (40)$$

with a common signal-to-noise ratio of 20dB. We vary w_6 between 0.035 and 0.090 in order to explore the super-resolution limits of our technique. Fig. 1 shows the detection performance in this case using the AIC criterion. To make some sort of comparison, we also analysed the performance of the standard AIC/MDL criteria for a similar six-source 12-sensor fully augmentable case (obviously) with the same Cramér-Rao bound, and found a similar detection performance.

6 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

We have demonstrated that estimation of an unknown number m of independent Gaussian signals incident upon a partially augmentable antenna array can be solved in the case where m exceeds the number of antenna sensors M and the number of the greatest contiguous lag $N_{\max}$. The proposed method adopts convex and linear programming algorithms that first convert the incomplete Toeplitz matrix into a (unstructured) ML p.d. Toeplitz matrix, and then into a sequence of structured p.d. Toeplitz matrices with a proper number of equal minimum eigenvalues. The final stage of the detection routine is to use traditional information criteria based on LR calculations to select the best candidate model. Comparison of the detection performance of this

Figure 1: Probability of correct detection.

method with the traditional AIC/MDL techniques applied to the corresponding M_α -sensor ULA with $m < M$ sources and identical CRB demonstrates similar detection performance.

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